

Evaluating Mental Health Policies for Middle School Students: Insights from Kunming City, Yunnan Province, China

Chunyu Li

College of Local Administration, Khon Kaen University, Khon Kaen, Thailand
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-7897-3684>

Peerasit Kamnuansilpa*

College of Local Administration, Khon Kaen University, Khon Kaen, Thailand
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6994-4809>

Xenia Ribaya Emperador-Garnace

College of Local Administration, Khon Kaen University, Khon Kaen, Thailand
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7938-5825>

*Corresponding author email: peerasit@kku.ac.th

Abstract

Background: The Chinese government has issued policies to promote the mental health and overall development of middle school students. However, mental health challenges among students remain significant, drawing widespread attention.

Objectives: This research assesses the effectiveness of mental health policies for middle school students in Kunming City, Yunnan Province, China, in addressing stakeholders' needs and implementing them efficiently.

Methodology: This qualitative study used a goal-free evaluation framework to gather data from 65 participants, including students, teachers, parents, community workers, psychiatrists, social workers, and psychological counsellors, through interviews and focus group discussions. Thematic analysis was conducted using NVivo 12 software.

Findings: The study found that while policies have improved students' mental health and social adaptability, challenges persist, including unequal resource distribution, low parental awareness, insufficient policy promotion, and difficulty tracking students' psychological states. Key influences on mental health include academic pressure, peer relationships, and family environment. A supportive setting built on trust, understanding, and recognition is essential for students' well-being.

Conclusion: The mental health of middle school students is dynamic and requires integrated efforts from schools, families, and society. Strengthening policy coordination and accessibility is critical to fostering sustainable school support systems.

Unique Contribution: This study advances the discourse on middle school student mental health in Kunming by shifting the focus from individual or school-based interventions to systemic coordination and proposing a new policy recommendation for collaborative mental health services.

Key Recommendations: To establish an integrated mental health support system for middle school students to enhance coordination among government agencies, schools, families, and professionals, which will also facilitate early detection, streamlined referrals, and resource sharing.

Keywords: Mental health policies, middle school students, Goal-Free Evaluation, Kunming City, Policy implementation

Introduction

The mental health of adolescents is a common issue in several countries around the world today. Statistics from the United Nations indicate that out of the 1.2 billion adolescents aged 15 to 24 worldwide, over 280 million are expected to have mental health issues (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2022). Similarly, the World Health Organisation estimates that globally, an estimated 14% of adolescents aged 10-19 experience mental health challenges, and many of them are not detected and untreated (World Health Organisation, 2021). Suppose mental concerns in adolescents are not adequately identified and addressed; the consequence can be severe, affecting their physical and emotional well-being, academic performance, interpersonal relationships, and other crucial aspects of life. In response to this pressing issue, governments worldwide have introduced policies aimed at addressing the mental health crises faced by middle school students.

Since 1992, the Chinese government has issued several policy documents on the mental health of middle school students to promote their physical and psychological health and overall development. Yunnan Province has formulated an implementation plan based on national policies and local realities. Kunming, the capital city of Yunnan Province, has actively responded to the call of national and provincial policies and provided timely and effective psychological support and counselling for middle school students.

The middle school period is a key stage for students' growth and a phase when significant changes occur in their bodies and minds. Students' emotions fluctuate considerably, and they are prone to feelings such as annoyance and anxiety. Providing mental health education to middle school students is a crucial way to promote students' mental health. However, the effective implementation of mental health education for middle school students depends on the support of mental health policies for those students. Therefore, it is necessary to evaluate the mental health policies for middle school students and to obtain relevant and accurate information on maintaining good mental health for students.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study were: (1) to investigate whether the mental health policies for middle school students in Kunming City, Yunnan Province, China, meet the needs of stakeholders, and (2) to assess how effectively these policies are implemented.

Literature Review

This section examines the theoretical foundations of the study, drawing on Goal-Free Evaluation (GFE), Stakeholder Theory, and Synergy Theory to establish a comprehensive framework for assessing the effectiveness of mental health policies for middle school students in Kunming.

Goal-Free Evaluation

Goal Free Evaluation (GFE) is an evaluation approach in which the evaluator assesses a programme without being influenced by predetermined goals and objectives (Youker, 2014). The primary aim of GFE is to establish a cause-and-effect relationship between project activities or services and their actual outcomes, enabling an unbiased assessment of the effectiveness. This method is particularly useful in complex environments where programmes may produce unintended or emergent results (Liu, 2019).

Given the complexity of mental health policies for middle school students, this study adopts the GFE framework to analyse whether these policies effectively address stakeholders' needs. Rather than focusing on predefined policy objectives, the research emphasises an open-ended exploration of policy outcomes. This approach ensures that the study captures both intended and unintended consequences, offering a comprehensive understanding of the policies' real-world impact. Additionally, by prioritising depth and contextual richness of the issue, the study seeks to uncover underlying causes contributing to the effectiveness or limitations of mental health policies in Kunming.

Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder Theory provides a framework for understanding individuals' and groups' diverse interests and roles as they are affected by an organisation's activities (Qi & Wu, 2018). This theory has been widely applied in education to analyse system development, policy formulation, and educational governance (Lu & Tang, 2022). Key stakeholders in education include governments, schools, teachers, students, and the community, each assuming roles such as coordinators, participants, beneficiaries, and regulators.

In the context of this study, the key stakeholders in mental health policy implementation include parents, students, teachers, psychiatrists, social workers, and psychological counsellors. Policymakers also play a role as stakeholders, shaping and enforcing policies. However, to maintain an unbiased assessment aligned with the GFE approach, this study does not include policymakers as interview participants, ensuring that the evaluation remains independent of policy-driven objectives. Instead, the research focuses on the experiences and perspectives of those directly affected by the policies.

Synergy Theory

Synergy theory examines the dynamic interactions between systems, emphasizing how collaboration and coordination contribute to system evolution and improved functionality (Zeng & Li, 2021). It highlights the transition from disorder to order and identifies system development principles across various disciplines.

Adolescent mental health issues are complex, necessitating a synergistic approach to policy implementation. Effective mental health interventions require collaboration among stakeholders, including government agencies, schools, families, hospitals, communities, and social psychological services organisations. This study considers synergy to explore interaction and examine whether their coordinated efforts enhance or hinder the effectiveness of mental health policies for middle school students in Kunming.

Methodology

This section outlines the research methodology, including the study design, population, sampling technique and size, data collection instruments, and data analysis procedures. By adopting a systematic and rigorous approach, this study ensures the reliability and validity of findings in evaluating mental health policies for middle school students in Kunming.

Research Design

This study adopts a qualitative research approach, emphasising participants' emotions and experiences while highlighting the importance of understanding issues from the researchers' perspective. The primary aim is to uncover social phenomena (Hong, 2013). The research is characterised by openness, flexibility, and adaptability, allowing an in-depth exploration of stakeholders' perceptions of mental health policies.

Population

The study was conducted in Kunming, Yunnan Province, China, a multi-ethnic city with a population of 8.68 million. Kunming has 207 junior high schools and 148 high schools, enrolling 380,128 students (Kunming Education and Sports Bureau, 2024). Given the city's diverse socio-cultural composition, students come from varied family backgrounds, contributing to differences in mental health challenges. Evaluating mental health policies in this context offers insights into psychological support needs and informs the development of more inclusive policies.

Sampling Technique and Sample Size

The study employed purposive sampling, selecting participants based on their relevance to the research objectives. To ensure a comprehensive analysis, key stakeholders—students, teachers, parents, community workers, psychiatrists, social workers, and psychological counsellors—were included.

To account for variations in school environments, schools were categorised into three levels—excellent, medium, and weak—based on overall performance. Two schools from each category were selected, ensuring diversity in school characteristics. Teachers recommended students and parents for participation, while colleagues, parents or teachers referred community workers, social workers, psychological counsellors, and psychiatrists.

A total of 16 students, 15 teachers (including principals, academic administrators, class teachers, and subject teachers), nine parents, eight community workers, nine social psychological services agency staff (four social workers and five psychological counsellors), and eight psychiatrists participated in the study. The overall guiding principle for determining sample size was data

saturation. Interviews continued until no new themes emerged, ensuring sufficient richness and diversity in the data (Mason, 2010; Morse, 1994). Additionally, six focus groups were formed with selected interviewees who provided insightful contributions, namely: 1) six students group, 2) six teachers group, 3) five parents group, 4) three community workers group, 5) four social psychological service agency staff group (comprising two social workers and two psychological counsellors), and 6) four psychiatrists group. The selection criteria for the in-depth interview and focus group participants are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: *The Selection Criteria for In-depth Interviewees and Focus Group Members*

Participant	Inclusion Criteria
Students	Recommended by the school teachers Students should be good at expressing their own ideas
Teachers	More than two years of teaching experience Responsible for school construction and planning classroom management
Parents	At least one of their kids studies in the school
Community Workers	More than 2 years of experience in community work
Social Workers, Psychological Counsellors	Have a psychology background Deal with the psychological problems of excessive students
Psychiatrists	With both a psychological and a medical background Over 2 years of working experience

Data Collection Instruments

In-depth interviews and focus group discussions served as the primary data collection methods. Researchers conducted interviews and group discussions from March to June 2024 using a hybrid online and offline approach. Each in-depth interview lasted 30-40 minutes, while the focus group discussion lasted on average for two hours. Given the comprehensiveness of the collected data, follow-up interviews were unnecessary. To ensure participant confidentiality, anonymity was maintained by assigning code names to interviewees, and all data were treated as confidential. Parents' consent was obtained for the students, and participants reviewed study details before their involvement.

Method of Data Analysis

This study employed thematic analysis to identify patterns and themes in the qualitative data systematically. The analysis followed five key steps: To extract key themes related to mental health from the data collected through interviews and focus groups, the process involved the following steps:

- (1) Familiarisation. The researchers transcribed and reviewed the audio recording and notes, removing irrelevant information and highlighting essential segments.
- (2) Generating Initial Codes. The researchers assigned codes to relevant text segments based on content.
- (3) Searching for Themes. The researchers grouped codes into potential themes based on their similarities.
- (4) Reviewing Themes. The researchers identified and refined themes to ensure accuracy and alignment with research objectives.
- (5) Defining and Naming Themes. Each theme was clearly defined, named, and described in detail.

To enhance analytical rigour, NVivo 12 software was used for data management, theme refinement, and visualisation of the relationships among key findings. Furthermore, data triangulation was employed to increase credibility and validity. This involved cross-verifying information from multiple sources to identify consistency and strengthen the reliability of findings (Cohen et al., 2002; Zhang, 2014). Triangulation also facilitated a comprehensive evaluation of mental health policies for middle school students, offering evidence-based recommendations for policy improvement.

In effect, this study integrates a qualitative research approach, purposive sampling, thematic analysis, and data triangulation to ensure a rigorous and in-depth evaluation of mental health policies in Kunming. The methodological framework enables a holistic understanding of stakeholders' perspectives, contributing to refining and enhancing mental health interventions for middle school students.

Findings

This section, based on the goal-free evaluation framework, provides a detailed analysis of each theme and associated activities, elaborating on the implementation of the mental policy for middle school students. The findings summarised in Tables 2 to 11 assess how well stakeholder needs are met during the policy implementation.

Through the analysis of interview and focus group discussion data, ten key themes were identified, namely: (1) Mental Health Education Course; (2) Publicity of Mental Health Policies; (3) Integration of Mental Health Education with Other Subjects; (4) Mental Health Education Training; (5) Mental Health Teachers' Team Building; (6) Psychological Counselling Services for Middle School Students; (7) Construction of Mental Health Archives for Middle School Students; (8) Psychological Intervention Services; (9) Hospital Treatment Services; and (10) Mental Health Tracking Services for Middle School Students.

Mental Health Education Course

Table 2: *Mental Health Education Course, Related Activities, and Stakeholders' Needs*

Theme	Activity	Stakeholders' Needs
Mental Health Education Course	Mental health knowledge explanation Mental health seminar Group Psychological Counselling Career Planning Psychodrama	Partially met

As presented in Table 2, interviews and focus group discussions revealed that schools offer mental health education courses primarily to comply with policy requirements. These courses typically cover explanations of mental health knowledge, mental health seminars, group psychological counselling, and career planning. They typically last 40 to 45 minutes every two weeks, with some schools developing school-based courses tailored to their specific needs. However, significant differences exist in the teaching staff between schools. High-performing schools generally have dedicated teams capable of developing customised curricula, while mental health classes positively impact students' self-awareness, emotional management, and interpersonal relationships.

Publicity of Mental Health Policies

Table 3: *Publicity of Mental Health Policies, Related Activities, and Stakeholders' Needs*

Theme	Activity	Stakeholders' Needs
Publicity of mental health policies	Campus publicity Online platform publicity Community publicity Media publicity	Partially met

As shown in Table 3, awareness and dissemination of mental health policies relied on publicity. Interviews revealed that students knew about the school's psychological counselling room, some were aware of the 12355 psychological service hotline, and a few mentioned the Kunming Youth Psychological Service Platform. Their understanding of mental health policies mainly came from school publicity. A common theme emerged: parents prioritise academics over mental health. Despite government efforts to promote policies online and through other channels, most parents were unaware of the availability of mental health service platforms. Community workers were familiar with policy documents, but community-level promotion remained limited. Social workers, including counsellors, showed greater awareness, while doctors focused primarily on policy aspects related to hospital treatment. The analysis of data indicates that, despite various publicity efforts, awareness of mental health policies remains uneven, with students relying on schools, parents largely uninformed, and professionals focusing on their specific roles.

Integration of Mental Health Education with Other Subjects

Table 4: *Integration of Mental Health Education with Other Subjects, Related Activities and Stakeholders' Needs*

Theme	Activity	Stakeholders' Needs
Integration of Mental Health Education with Other Subjects	Integration of mental health and ideological and political courses No less than 1 hour of physical exercise every day Integration of psychology courses and labour courses Integration of Mental Health and Arts Curriculum	Partially met

As presented in Table 4, integrating mental health education into the school curriculum remains a challenge. Under the Five Education framework--moral, intellectual, physical, aesthetic, and labor education--introduced by the Yunnan Provincial Department of Education in 2024, schools are required to embed mental health education into moral instruction, reduce academic pressure, use sports and arts to emotional regulation, and incorporate labor education to develop the skills. While well-resourced schools offer music and art to support students' mental well-being, others struggle due to limited resources. Teachers, primarily focused on academics, rarely integrate psychological well-being into their lessons beyond the Five Education. As a result, mental health education remains inconsistently applied across schools.

Mental Health Education Training

Table 5: *Mental Health Education Training, Related Activities, and Stakeholders' Needs*

Theme	Activity	Stakeholders' Needs
Mental health education training	Teacher Training Parents of students Training	Partially met

Table 5 shows that the effectiveness of mental health training for middle school teachers and parents remains uneven. Psychology teachers and class teachers receive centralised training, with full-time psychology teachers completing over 20 hours. Class teachers undergo mental health training online, but subject teachers receive minimal training, and parents only have occasional sessions--usually once per term, sometimes through community lectures.

Although training follows Yunnan Province's policies, its impact is limited. Many parents disregard mental health education, believing their children have no issues and that psychological knowledge is unnecessary. Only a few show concerns, typically after problems arise. As a result, early intervention remains difficult, as most parents struggle to recognise psychological issues in advance.

Mental Health Teachers' Team Building

Table 6: *Mental Health Teachers Team Building, Related Activities, and Stakeholders' Needs*

Theme	Activity	Stakeholders' Needs
Mental health teacher team building	Construction of the teaching staff of mental health education in middle schools The construction of out-of-school middle school students' mental health teacher team	Partially met

As presented in Table 6, effective team building and collaboration are crucial for addressing the growing demand for mental health support in schools. As found in the interviews and focus group discussion, policy requirements mandate that schools have one or two designated mental health teachers responsible for teaching psychological courses and providing counselling services. However, some of these teachers serve in part-time roles, juggling multiple responsibilities, including subject teaching. To address the shortage of in-school mental health staff, the Kunming Youth Mental Health Service Centre was established in 2022, offering support through a free 12355 youth psychological hotline.

In the same year, Yunnan Provincial Psychiatric Hospital launched an internet hospital for psychological services, providing online consultations, assessments, and treatment. These initiatives help bridge the gap in mental health support within schools. However, the absence of a coordinated strategy for off-campus mental health services often forces schools to hire external psychologists to meet student needs independently. Therefore, a more integrated collaborative approach between schools and external mental health providers is essential to ensuring consistent and comprehensive support for students.

Psychological Counselling Services

Table 7: *Psychological Counselling Services, Related Activities, and Stakeholders' Needs*

Theme	Activity	Stakeholders' Needs
Psychological counselling services for middle school students	Construction of a psychological counselling activity room Psychological Counselling Referral Service Psychological Assessment	Partially met

As shown in Table 7, increased financial investment in mental health education has played a crucial role in expanding psychological counselling services for students. Overall, the Kunming Municipal Finance Bureau has significantly increased funding for mental health education in recent years, with allocation rising from 2.45 million yuan in 2021 (Kunming Municipal Finance Bureau, 2021) to 4.75 million yuan in 2022 (Kunming Municipal Finance Bureau, 2023). This growth reflects

the government’s increasing commitment to enhancing mental health services, which includes counselling services for middle school students.

In response to the shortage of in-school psychological counsellors, off-campus professionals have become an essential supplement. Effective collaboration between on-campus and off-campus services is necessary for managing students’ electronic mental health records, psychological assessments, referrals, crisis interventions, and other related tasks. However, interviews revealed a critical challenge: student psychological records are not stored in a unified system. As a result, schools primarily rely on information provided by parents and students to track external counselling sessions. This fragmented data collection process can leave gaps in understanding students’ mental health needs, making it easier for teachers to overlook emerging psychological concerns. Establishing a more integrated data-sharing mechanism between schools and external mental health providers would enhance early intervention and ensure students receive comprehensive support.

Construction of Mental Health Archives

Table 8: Construction of Mental Health Archives, Related Activities, and Stakeholders' Needs

Theme	Activity	Stakeholders' Needs
Construction of mental health archives for middle school students	Psychological consultation records Record of psychological assessment results Management of mental health records Psychological crisis intervention record Track service records	Partially met

As presented in Table 8, recognising that comprehensive mental health archives are crucial for improving psychological support, Kunming conducts annual psychological assessments for middle school students, maintaining individual psychological profiles in line with Yunnan Province’s 2020 Mental Health Policy. However, tracking students who seek treatment outside of school remains challenging. The hospital system operates independently, making it difficult for schools to gain a full understanding of students’ mental health.

To bridge this gap, schools typically rely on communication with parents to obtain information about external psychological services, However, this approach often results in incomplete data and overlooked concerns, as parents may not always provide detailed or accurate updates Strengthening coordination between schools, health care providers, and families is essential for ensuring a more integrated and effective mental health support system for students.

Psychological Intervention Services

Table 9: Psychological Intervention Services, Related Activities, and Stakeholders' Needs

Theme	Activity	Stakeholders' Needs
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Psychological intervention services	After the psychological assessment, students with psychological problems undergo intervention. Teachers or parents of students discover abnormal behaviour of students and provide psychological intervention to the students Psychological crisis intervention	Partially met
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In recent years, Kunming City has conducted annual psychological assessment activities for middle school students. Based on the results presented in Table 9, students are analysed and categorised by mental health status. Teachers are responsible for mental health, class management, and counselling for students exhibiting warning signs. For those with severe psychological concerns, schools notify parents and recommend seeking further diagnosis at a hospital. While the government and schools emphasise student mental health, current interventions rely heavily on assessment scales and direct communication. However, given the dynamic and complex nature of adolescent mental health, these methods have limitations. A more comprehensive, multi-dimensional approach is needed--one that integrates early detection, continuous support, and collaboration between schools, families, and health care professionals.

Hospital Treatment Services

Table 10: *Hospital Treatment Services, Activities, and Stakeholders' Needs*

Theme	Activity	Stakeholders' Needs
Hospital treatment services	Psychotherapy Treatment of mental illness	Met

As shown in Table 10, hospitals play a vital role in providing psychological services, which are becoming increasingly accessible through digital platforms. Most hospitals have psychology departments and offer psychotherapy services. The Yunnan Medical apps enable patients to register and book appointments in advance. Some hospitals also provide online registration, eliminating wait times. Consultation times are displayed on the apps, allowing patients to schedule visits conveniently. Students have noted that accessing psychological care is now much easier.

Mental Health Tracking Services

Table 11: *Mental Health Tracking Services, Related Activities, and Stakeholders' Needs*

Theme	Activity	Stakeholders' Needs
Mental health tracking service	Post-treatment services for mental illness	Not met

	Tracking service after psychological crisis intervention Tracking service for students with abnormal psychological assessment results	
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As illustrated in Table 11, interviews and focus group discussions revealed that follow-up services for middle school students' mental health pose the most significant challenge. Prevention, diagnosis, treatment, crisis intervention, and follow-up are complex, requiring collaboration among teachers, parents, psychiatrists, social workers, psychological counsellors, and community workers. Only a well-coordinated support network can provide adequate assistance to students facing mental health issues.

In practice, lack of coordination often leads to a delay in monitoring students' mental health status, preventing timely intervention. Despite these challenges, stakeholders agree that the policy has contributed to students' mental well-being and improved their social adaptability.

Unexpected Discovery

Two key findings emerged through interviews and focus group discussions: (1) Academic Pressure, Interpersonal Relationships, and Family Environment as Key Factors. Students identified academic pressure, interpersonal relationships, and family environment as critical factors influencing their mental health; (2) The Need for Respect, Understanding, and Trust. Students expressed that their greatest need is to feel respected, understood, and trusted by parents and teachers. Many students stated that their happiness depends on the support and recognition they receive from their families and educators.

Discussions

This study highlights the complexity of middle school students' mental health in China, shaped by multiple stakeholders and societal dynamics. While mental health policies in Kunming City, Yunnan Province, have contributed to improving students' well-being and social adaptability, significant challenges remain in their implementation. The uneven distribution of urban and rural education resources, as well as geographical location, economic development level and other factors, has caused an imbalance in mental health education resources (Zhang et al., 2022). This limits the effective implementation of policies.

Furthermore, the fragmented system of psychological record-keeping makes it difficult to track students' mental health progress, reducing the impact of interventions. Compounding these challenges is the weak promotion of mental health services, resulting in limited awareness among students and parents about available resources.

This study aligns with previous research (e.g. Steare et al. 2023), demonstrating the profound impact of academic pressure, family relationships, and social stigma on students' mental health. Consistent with Erikson's (1968) classical theory of personality development, this study underscores students' need for an environment built on trust, recognition, and affirmation. Without such support, mental health challenges may be exacerbated by feelings of isolation and inadequacy. Addressing these issues requires a comprehensive, stakeholder-driven approach that

integrates schools, families, and society to establish a coordinated support system and promote the development of key mental health abilities and comprehensive personality of middle school students (Huang, 2024).

By employing Goal Free Evaluation (GFE), this study moves beyond assessing predefined policy objectives to examine the actual effects of policies on students. The findings underscore the need for equitable distribution of mental health resources, stronger policy coordination, and improved awareness efforts to ensure accessibility. Effective mental health governance requires adaptability, inclusivity, and responsiveness to students' lived experiences. Moving forward, policies should prioritize the integration of psychological support within educational frameworks, fostering an ecosystem that nurtures students' mental resilience and long-term well-being.

Conclusion

The mental health of middle school students is dynamic and requires integrated efforts from schools, families, and society. Strengthening policy coordination, accessibility, and early intervention mechanisms is essential to ensuring more effective and responsive student mental health services.

Limitations

While this study provides insight into mental health policies for middle school students in Kunming, several limitations must be considered. Relying primarily on qualitative data, the research captures stakeholder perceptions but lacks the generalisability of large-scale quantitative studies. Future research should adopt mixed-method approaches to enhance comprehensiveness. Additionally, the study focuses mainly on policy beneficiaries--students, parents and educators--while policymakers, mental health professionals, and school administrators receive less attention. This may result in an incomplete understanding of the institutional constraints affecting policy implementation. Furthermore, the findings are region-specific, limiting broader applicability. Kunming's unique socioeconomic, cultural, and educational contexts may not reflect conditions in other provinces. Comparative studies across multiple regions could improve the external validity of these findings.

Limited access to psychological records and policy implementation data also constrains insights into long-term policy outcomes. A longitudinal analysis of students' mental health trajectories could provide a more robust evaluation. Lastly, social desirability bias may have influenced responses, as mental health stigma could lead some participants to moderate their views in interviews and discussions.

Policy Recommendations

Despite these limitations, this study advanced policy evaluation by shifting from a goal-based framework to a stakeholder-driven assessment, emphasising the real-world impact of policies beyond their formal objective.

Based on the findings of this study, we recommend establishing an integrated mental health support system for middle school students to enhance coordination among government agencies,

schools, families, and professionals, which will also facilitate early detection, streamlined referrals, and resource sharing.

The key leverage point is structural collaboration through mandatory cross-sector case meetings, shared digital data systems, and joint capacity building programmes. Public awareness initiatives should also be implemented to reduce stigma and encourage early help-seeking, including targeted information campaigns and community engagement. By institutionalising, cooperation, enhancing service efficiency, and fostering proactive intervention, these measures will not only strengthen but ensure that mental health support is more accessible, responsive, and sustainable.

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